

Slab-pile foundation

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Annotation. One of the most effective developments in the field of foundation construction of the last decade is combined slab-pile foundations - PSF. The motivation for their active study and implementation in practice are the general problems of building foundations - an increase in the number of storeys of buildings and a corresponding increase in loads on foundations, a gradually emerging shortage of "good" soils, a high density of urban development and the often arising need to build tightly adjacent to existing structures, etc. .P.

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PSF is a monolithic slab, supported by piles of one type or another and located in the form of a pile field, belts, bushes or single piles. The defining feature of the PSF, however, is not the fact that there are two components - slab and pile, but the fact that both components of the foundation are load-bearing, providing direct transfer of the load from the above-foundation structure to the base soil: piles - with the lower end and side surface, slab - with the base ... To be able to include the grillage slab into the work to repel the soil, at least two conditions must be present (in addition to the obvious requirement for the grillage to be directly supported on the ground): the pile component of the SSF must have a certain flexibility, i.e. development of settlement under load: in a monolithic slab - grillage, there should be areas that are sufficiently distant in plan from the piles.

The first requirement means, in particular, that pile foundations with piles resting on solid incompressible rocky soils, excluding the possibility of sediment development, cannot be classified as PFR.

The second requirement reflects the fact that a full-fledged rebuff along the bottom of the grillage can be realized only in areas that are sufficiently remote from the piles, outside the zone of their influence. This effect is manifested in the involvement of the near-pile soil in the total settlement with the pile, the formation of a "sediment funnel". The possibility of turning on the stove is present only in the area outside these funnels. Traditional options for cluster or band grillages, practically repeating in plan the configuration of the corresponding groups of piles, usually do not provide such an opportunity, as well as large-sized slabs in plan, arranged along a "dense" grid of piles (pile field) with a pile pitch of no more than 4 d. The first regulation of slab-pile (or - in the normative terminology - pile-slab) foundations took place in SP 52-102-2003 "Design and construction of pile foundations". In our opinion, the approach implemented in the specified norms cannot be regarded as successful. In fact, the concept of a PSF was adopted with a pile component in the form of a regular pile field, with a pile pitch of 5 - 8 d. This step is slightly higher than the 3d step, which is traditional for hanging piles, and allows the central sections of the inter-pile intervals of the slab to be connected to work. However, the very insignificant total area of such plots also predetermines a rather low share of the total load that can be transferred to the slab component of the PSF - no more than

15%, according to the specified Standards. In general, in this joint venture, the slab-pile foundation is interpreted as some development and expansion of the capabilities of the traditional pile foundation, which remains basic and basic. A later revision of the Norms - SP 24.13330.2011, Updating SNiP 2.02.03.85 "Pile Foundations", expanded the concept of the PSF by removing the restrictions noted above. This allows us to propose a slightly different approach to PSF, implemented in the works of the Ural school of foundation engineering. Within the framework of this approach, the basic, initial type of foundation is a slab foundation on a natural basis. or other requirements of the calculation of deformations, the transition to the slab-pile option is carried out with the setting of a certain number of reinforcing piles. The most rational is placing piles in the form of bushes or next to them in the support zones of load-bearing columns and walls with a minimum step. - inter-row and inter-row - areas, and not to interpile. At the same time, there are no restrictions in the share of the load taken by the slab PSF. The following typical situations can be distinguished, in which it is advisable (and sometimes no alternative) to use slab-pile foundations.

- Weak and loose soils.
- Uneven compressibility of the base.
- Adjacent to existing foundations.

When calculating a pile foundation, it is necessary to take into account the simultaneous operation of the pile and the slab. With the exception of foundations, in which a gap is left between the top of the piles and the slab part of the grillage, in order to turn on the slab, a displacement (settlement) of the foundation of several tens of mm is required, while the pile, which requires a few mm to gain the maximum bearing capacity, will already be "ripped off" (the limiting resistance along the lateral surface will be overcome). This places special demands on the strength of the pile in terms of material and pile testing program. It is necessary to determine both the minimum N_{min} and the maximum N_{max} bearing capacity of the piles on the ground in accordance with the conditions. The calculation of the pile-slab foundation must be performed for both values of the bearing capacity of the piles on the ground:

$$N_{min} = y_0 \times F_d / (y_n \times y_k);$$

$$N_{max} = y_0 \times F_d \times y_n \times y_k$$

y_0 - coefficient of working conditions; F_d - bearing capacity of the pile, y_n - reliability factor for the intended

purpose; γ_k - coefficient of reliability on the ground.

Conclusion: To date, the existing methods for solving this problem. The disadvantages of the known structures of the pile-slab foundation are: significant labor intensity; relatively low bearing capacity per unit volume

of material; complex interaction of the grillage with piles and piles with soil, depending on the jointly acting vertical load, horizontal force and bending moment; undefined participation of the grillage in contact with the ground.